

Farm machinery

Spiral pump: a low-cost, rational, stream-driven water-lifting device

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The search for low-cost pumps that can be powered by renewable energy sources and built out of available materials by local craftsmen is a high research priority among agricultural engineers.

Recently the stream-driven spiral pump has been re-discovered. The pump resembles a large wheel with its axis parallel to the water surface (Fig. 1). When partially submerged in a stream, the flow rotates the wheel so that alternate slugs of water and air are scooped into the intake tube.

The heart of the pump is a coiled flexible plastic hose. The end of the hose leads into the rotating axle. By means of a wivel, water moves into a stationary water delivery pipe. During water delivery, the individual slugs in each loop of the hose are forced against the head, resulting in buildup of differential pressure in each loop.

We built a prototype spiral pump with 2.0 m outer diameter to determine the parameters that influence its performance. To simulate different flow streams under laboratory conditions, the pump was immersed in a water tank and rotated by an electric motor. A strain gauge was attached to the axle to determine efficiency and maximum torque.

Parameters evaluated were water volume delivered per time to a defined height at a specified rotational speed, tube diameter, number of coils in the spiral and sum of coil diameters, and volume of water scooped into the pump at each turn of the wheel.

Influence of each parameter on performance was determined through multiple stepwise regression analysis. This showed that the lower the rotational speed of the pump and the higher the total

head, the greater the efficiency (efficiency reached more than 50%) (Fig.2).

The maximum torque to rotate the pump without any impact on rotational speed is influenced mainly by the total head and tube diameter. The larger the tube diameter used, the higher the torque required to turn the wheel. Small tube diameters also proved to add to pump efficiency.

Regardless of the volume of water scooped in, it is not possible to fill the outer coil to more than 50%.

The most efficient combination of design parameters for the spiral pump were found to be high head, slow rotational speed, scoop volume 100-120% of outer coil, and small tube diameters.

Knowing the kinetic energy of a given stream and the drag coefficient of the paddles of the pump, it is now possible to design pumps where all factors are well matched, allowing the most efficient kinetic energy utilization of a given stream flow for pumping purposes. ■

1. Overview of the spiral pump.

2. Predicted delivered water volume and average efficiency versus total head at different speeds of rotation.